

ENHANCED SCHOOL GUIDANCE AND COUNSELING PROGRAM FOR STUDENTS' PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to identify an enhanced school guidance and counseling program for students' personality development. The descriptive research design and researcher-made survey questionnaire were used in gathering and collecting data. The mean, standard deviation, and Pearson-r correlation were utilized to analyze the result. The research included 80 Open High School Program students (OHSP) from grades 7 to 10 of Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School. The study indicated that guidance and counseling programs include students' personality, behavior, curriculum, learning environment, teachers, and parents. Results show a significant relationship between the guidance and counseling program-related factors and the student's personality development that imply they are essential features to consider when implementing a structured guidance and counseling program to assist individuals' cognitive, psychosocial, and emotional development. The findings concluded significant relationships between the guidance and counseling program-related factors and the student's personality development. Based on the study, it is recommended that: 1) School guidance counselors may be encouraged to develop programs and activities that help students develop their personalities. Teachers may be made aware of the significance of their roles and their attitudes and actions. Students may be taught in a way that allows them to gain a better understanding of their personal growth. The family may be advised to develop a better understanding of their children's total wellbeing.

Keywords: personality, behavior, curriculum, learning environment, teachers, parents, personality development